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Vitamin D: Youth For Ever

Vitamin D is the most important vitamin for the human body. It is akin to chlorophyll in plants. The two are similar in their importance for metabolic processes and in their close relationship with sunlight, specifically ultraviolet rays.

Benefits:

It maintains normal levels of calcium and phosphorus in the blood. In doing so, it preserves bone mass in the human body. It is used in the prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. Its role is fundamental in metabolism. Numerous studies have linked obesity to Vitamin D deficiency in the body. It plays an important role in preventing cancerous diseases, such as breast cancer. It is also crucial in preventing Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and in prolonging the time between attacks for those afflicted with it. Vitamin D supports the body's immunity against infections. Not to be forgotten is its significant role in alleviating symptoms for patients with diabetes and hypertension. These are just some of its most important benefits, among many others.

Important Note: *A recent study showed that a daily dose (2000 International Units) of Vitamin D is sufficient to prevent aging and its chronic diseases.*

Sources:

Its presence in food is relatively low. It is found in fatty fish like salmon, cod liver oil, egg yolks, and cheeses. Relying on natural foods alone cannot meet the body's daily requirements for Vitamin D. Conversely, human skin can synthesize a sufficient amount of Vitamin D, but under specific conditions:

- 1. Direct skin contact with sunlight: The presence of glass, sunscreen, clothing, etc., all reduce the skin's efficiency in producing Vitamin D.*

2. *Duration of sun exposure: This is related to skin tone. For example, fair skin may only need half an hour to produce the body's daily requirement of Vitamin D. Darker skin may need 2 to 4 hours to produce the same amount. The duration increases significantly for those with very dark skin, reaching approximately 6 to 8 hours.*

3. *Surface area of exposed skin: The amount of Vitamin D produced by the skin of the face alone is less than that produced by the face and both upper limbs, for instance.*

4. *Time of sun exposure: Some believe that the sun at sunset or in the morning is effective for producing an ample amount of Vitamin D. This is a misconception. The optimal time is midday, from 10 am until 3 pm, when the sun is directly overhead.*

Important Note: *Due to increasing air pollution and the high concentration of suspended particles, the amount of ultraviolet rays reaching the Earth's surface has diminished. Consequently, the skin's efficiency in synthesizing Vitamin D has significantly decreased. City dwellers are the most affected by this.*

Daily Requirement:

This has changed considerably from what it was in the past. The adult human body needs 1200 to 1650 International Units of Vitamin D daily. This is obtained from food, from skin synthesis, and from artificially fortified foods with Vitamin D. Due to the relatively strict conditions for skin synthesis of Vitamin D and its scarcity in natural foods, it is preferable to rely on the pharmaceutical industry to meet the requirement for Vitamin D. This is a personal conviction specific to Vitamin D.

Dosage and Administration:

I recommend a daily dose of Vitamin D, amounting to 2000 International Units. It is preferably taken after breakfast, along with one or two 500mg calcium pills (equivalent to 200 or 400 mg of elemental calcium), depending on age. I do not recommend large weekly or monthly doses for the following reason:

The digestive absorption of Vitamin D is relatively weak. For millions of years, the human body has relied on skin synthesis to meet its Vitamin D needs. Because Vitamin D is relatively scarce in natural foods, the human body has not developed

high efficiency in its digestive system for absorbing it. Personally, I believe that 4000 IU is the maximum digestive absorption capacity for this vitamin. This belief is based on numerous clinical and laboratory indicators. In one study, it was found that administering a high dose of Vitamin D (50,000 IU daily for three months) did not cause its blood concentration to rise to toxic levels.

Therefore, there is no benefit in giving high weekly or monthly doses of Vitamin D. They give a false sense of adequate prevention or treatment efficacy, while the reality is the opposite. Furthermore, daily doses higher than 4000 IU will suffer the same fate of being wasted and ineffective.

Important Note: Vitamin D toxicity is very rare. Some studies have noted the absence of toxic concentrations of Vitamin D in the blood despite treatment with very high daily doses of 50,000 IU for several months. This clearly supports my above conclusion regarding the weak digestive absorption of Vitamin D.

Important Note: Measuring Vitamin D levels is imprecise for monitoring and follow-up. It is known that the primary derivative of Vitamin D, 25-hydroxycalciferol, has a relatively long half-life (3 weeks). As such, it does not accurately reflect the body's Vitamin D reserves. Meanwhile, the second, active derivative of Vitamin D, 1-25 Dihydroxycholecalciferol, is considered more accurate for evaluation and follow-up. Personally, I do not rely on either; instead, I recommend proceeding with prevention or treatment with Vitamin D as I have described, for the reasons I have presented.

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